

Benchmarks for Fair Inequality. Wealth Distribution, Causes of Observed Findings

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There is material in the media and academic literature about economic inequality, which in most instances converge to inequality in income and wealth distribution across population and geographical strata. In a public domain the word “inequality” is often associated with unfairness, although intuitively people generally feel unfairness towards excessive inequality, while accepting inequality as such as a normal feature of life. Indeed, people are widely unequal in all possible dimensions - physically, intellectually, in social and material status, living conditions, upbringing, country of residence, and so on. However, then, an obvious conclusion should follow that it is rather natural arrangement that people have different incomes and wealth in their possession. However, as with any phenomenon, there is a measure, an optimum, when such inequality works for the good of society, while deviation from this optimum accordingly worsens the societies well being. Here, an approach based on analogies with distribution of nutritional resources in natural food chains, in particular among unicellular and multicellular organisms, is presented. However surprising and disconnected from the human societies such an approach can be viewed at first, nonetheless there are arguments that there is such a connection. Also certain numerical parameters are introduced, which can be used for quantitative evaluation of inequality of income and wealth distributions from the perspective of its divergence from the distributions, which are considered optimal based on proposed approaches.

The fact of life is that people are unequal in all possible measures. However, then, an obvious conclusion should follow that it is rather natural arrangement that people have different incomes and wealth in their possession. In this regard, all social and economic theories and teachings assuming uniform distribution of social status and material resources are utopias. Even if implemented, such socioeconomic arrangements do not sustain long.

Economic position of a population’s stratum generally closely correlates with its social and political standing, and vice versa. Once people acquire wealth, they aim for power and higher social position. *Quantity* of wealth defines the *qualitative* nature of the social class a person belongs to. (Less prominent used to be the reverse trend, but in the last two decades people who got a high office position in a military or government monetize it with much greater enthusiasm, since the public opinion was more and more instilled with an idea of wealth possession as a measure of life success.) Thus, it makes sense to use the notion of *socioeconomic* classes, even though exceptions are possible (say, some group may be wealthy, but for religious or other reasons is restricted in power).

The most known teachings about equal distribution are political ideology of Marxism and its offspring ideologies, whose implementation brought lots of hardships to people in those countries. (We do not talk about its economical part, which has useful findings.) Marxism is an extremist ideological teaching in its core principles, and so it appealed very much to people with extremist inclinations, which on the basis of Marxism went even to greater extremes, as well as propagated the same flawed ideas into other domains of human life, like culture in general and arts in particular, pedagogy, science, etc. It is not that dialectical laws, of which Marx became aware from Hegel’s philosophical teaching, are untrue. They are. It just that Marx applied them fragmentarily, sporadically, and because of that in a terribly wrong way, to such complex phenomenon as human societies. For practical purposes, laws of dialectical materialism must be applied in their *entirety* to produce adequate inferences. Marx did not do that. Instead, he invented *historical materialism*, which has little in common with dialectical materialism, arbitrary and *very much* inconsistently using certain categories and notions of dialectical materialism (whose origin can be traced to teachings of ancient Ionian philosophers, first of all Anaximander). For instance, he missed a critical for such analysis dialectical category *measure*, as well as ignored many other fundamental tenets of dialectics, even in its Hegel’s meaning. (More so with

regard to dialectical materialism, to which development he contributed not a single paragraph, concentrating exclusively on economical issues and ideological, political struggle, including practical political activity). Neither the notion of socioeconomic classes, used in his analysis and known well before Marx, is untrue. We see these classes, its political representations and antagonism between them on everyday basis. It's an idea of inevitable *hegemony of one class, proletariat*, which is deeply wrong in Marxist ideology.

Ironically, in most western countries presently the situation mirrors this same extrimistic Marxists' postulate, when a minuscule in quantity class of the wealthiest, the global oligarchy, is that same *hegemon*, which dictatorially and ruthlessly rules the countries and much of the world, with even more dire political and economical consequences for the rest of population. No proletariat ever ruled any country, and it certainly could not, so we don't know, what such a rule would be. However, we have more than enough proofs today that the rule of one class, of the modern oligarchy, brings only more and more troubles and miseries to the rest of us (as it always was the case with oligarchic rulers). It is only when some balance of power of all classes exists, some socioeconomic harmony is possible. (Denmark and Sweden 30-40 years ago could be not ideal, but approximate examples of such countries with balanced representation of economic interests of different socioeconomic classes of population.)

It is intuitively clear that the society's organization would be more functional, and maybe even optimal and fair from the perspective of quality of life of its members, if variations in *personal* abilities to produce material, intellectual and societal goods and values match the remuneration, which members of the society receive.

However, measuring such personal variations is difficult, and even more difficult implementing such socioeconomic systems. Without delving into the proofs, of which the humankind presently empirically received many, neither the uniformly equal distribution of societal resources between its members, nor extreme material and social inequality present optimal (from the perspective of quality of life) socioeconomic systems. Oligarchic and plutocratic governess as a rule of thumb leads to societal destruction and social unrest. Examples of relatively equal distribution of income and wealth on a large scale are few, and it is not equal distribution alone, but a combination of factors, of which the equal distribution was hardly the main one, which demised such societies. (As a side note, people much more willingly accept equal distribution, especially if there is still some room for variations in income and wealth, and real possibility to significantly advance on the social ladder, than excessive inequality. A higher position in social hierarchy, which exists in any society, by itself is a quality substitute for material status, especially when social security is high and people are confident in their future. There are good and bad (for the societal development) reasons that the great majority of people are alright with about equal distribution, but this discussion is outside of our topic.)

So, the income and wealth inequality is an *inherent* and *natural* feature of human societies. But how to find that "golden mean", an optimal inequality, which would serve best the societal overall well being? Here, an approach is presented, which is based on analogies with distribution of nutritional resources in natural food chains, in particular among unicellular and multicellular organisms. Also, we introduce certain numerical parameters, which can be used for *quantitative* evaluation of inequality of income and wealth distributions from the perspective of their divergence from the distributions, which are considered optimal based on proposed approaches. It is important to have such objective criteria, since the presently often used Gini coefficient and Lorentz curve have limited practical value. Indeed, in Gini coefficient one reference point corresponds to a uniform equality of wealth or income distribution, which is a highly hypothetical scenario, and the other reference point is when few own everything and the rest nothing, which is also an unrealistic dream of some riches they work on to implement.

The paper consists of two parts having distinct formats. The first part presents the approach in a format similar to a research paper, i. e. with figures, tables, simple formulas, although it is still accessible to a wider audience. The second part analyzes and explains the obtained results in a plain language. To a large extent, this is a self-sufficient text.

Distribution of nutritional resources in natural food chains

Research papers [1-3] present results of studies how and why the metabolic rate E (amount of energy produced per unit of time) of unicellular and multicellular organisms changes in a certain mathematically well defined way when mass M of organisms increases. Namely that

$$(1) E = a \cdot M^b,$$

where parameter b is called “metabolic allometric exponent”, a is a constant. The value of b is usually less than one, which means that the metabolic energy E increases *slower* than mass M . The above equation can be rewritten as

$$(2) \log(E) = \log(a) + b \cdot \log(M)$$

Formula (2) is an equation of a *straight line* with a slope b and intercept $c = \log(a)$. Fig. 1 shows such a dependence of metabolic rate E from volume for unicellular organisms in logarithmic coordinates, for the entire range of masses, that is from the smallest organism *B. subtilis* to the biggest one *Amoeba*. (Volume in this case strongly correlates with mass.) Note how well the points corresponding to particular organisms fit the straight regression line. The value of allometric exponent is $b = 0.758$. (This value is for the end of growth, while for the beginning of growth it is 0.853.)

Fig. 1. Change of metabolic rate depending on volume for unicellular organisms, in logarithmic scale. Numbered data points correspond to *B. subtilis* (1), *Staphylococcus* (2), *E. coli 1* (3), *E. coli 2* (4), *S. pombe* (5), *Amoeba* (6).

Similar straight lines well approximate change of metabolic rate with mass increase for *multicellular* organisms [2]. Table 1 shows values of allometric exponents for different multicellular organisms.

Table 1. Summary of allometric exponents.
MMR - maximal metabolic rate (MR); BMR - basal MR.

<i>Animals</i>	<i>MMR</i>	<i>BMR</i>
Mammals	0.871-0.88	0.682
Athletic mammals	0.942-0.985	
Reptiles	0.89-0.92	0.767
Fish	0.976	
Birds	0.84-0.88	0.644-0.67

The amount of produced energy (metabolic rate) very closely correlates with the amount of consumed nutrients (this relationship is discussed in detail in works [1-3]). So, we may think of mathematical dependencies presented on Fig. 1 as a description of amount of nutritional resources each species in a food chain of a certain common habitat obtains.

The effect of metabolic allometric scaling was described by Kleiber in 1932, but until recently its causes were unknown. It is only in the last decade the idea that it is due to natural selection began to suffice. But what kind of selection? It was shown nine years ago in the first versions of works [1,2] that such a metabolic allometric scaling is due to evolutionary *group selection* within the *entire food chain*. This is an *optimal* balance nature found during evolution process, which best serves the purpose of preservation and stability of the *entire* food chain. It is namely such a distribution of nutrients within the food chain, which allows for each species to survive obtaining enough nutrients to reproduce in sufficient quantities, while not too much to explode in population, and thus jeopardizing existence of other species of the food chain they prey on or share common resources with; this way preventing destruction of the entire food chain. General public is usually familiar with a popular notion “survival of the fittest” in the theory of natural selection, less knowing the words “adaptive selection”. However, the actual mechanism of natural selection includes also *group* selection, which is of no less importance as the individual selection is. In fact, one is impossible without the other. The notion of group selection is a new development; even many biologists of the older school have difficulty accepting these presently proven ideas.

It is important to note that exactly the same mechanism of nutrients distribution within the food chains was obtained *independently*, by *different* methods, both for unicellular and multicellular organisms. These independent discoveries of the same group selection mechanism for so different organisms much increase the credibility of obtained results. It is also worth noting that both considered groups of organisms have close values of relative differences in maximal and minimal mass, *and* in maximal and minimal metabolic rate (which is equivalent to relative difference in maximal and minimal nutrient consumption). Of course, at a first glance it seems that trying to compare in a similar way distribution of wealth in human societies is a far fetched exercise, since the structure of consumption in human societies is different from the animal world. In fact, the author thought the same way until more revealing results were obtained, which are presented in this paper.

Distribution of nutrient consumption in animals and wealth distribution in human societies

Comparing animal communities and human societies is of course a tricky exercise. Still, both consume and share resources, and in both instances this happens within a certain common habitat. Comparing patterns of distribution of resources can give some insights and provide quantitative criteria for analysis of such distributions from different perspectives. At the same time, one should keep in mind that wealth is not an amorphous but a complex structured entity, including different interlinked and interdependent corporations, trusts and host of other enterprises and organizations, including governmental and public ones, which in turn are intricately interconnected. Thus, the obtained results and some discovered regularities apparently can be applied on a broader scale, such as analysis of wealth of corporations and of wealth structure in general.

It turned out that the wealth distribution of the wealthy part of population, of about top 10%, excluding the very rich above one hundredth percent, is indeed well approximated by a straight line in logarithmic coordinates - very similarly to Fig. 1. It is only the bottom 90% of population fall well below this straight line. On the other hand, the distribution of wealth of the richest goes above this line. The wealth of the top 0.1% is estimated at 20-27% of wealth of the entire population. (A range of 20-27% is indicated because results of such estimations vary a lot depending on the calculation methodology [4-6].) However, even more surprising was the result that the slope of this line is close to values of allometric exponents describing nutrient distribution in food chains of natural habitats. These effects are unlikely to be a coincidence, and there are also certain systemic level considerations which indicate in the same direction (which we have no space to discuss here). If so, that would mean that some group selective mechanisms, defining distribution of wealth resources, work in this range similarly to animal world, while below and above this range the working of these mechanisms is suppressed by some factors. (Some of these factors are actually on the surface, and will be discussed later.)

Composing graphs of wealth distribution. Data for the USA in 2016

Now, how can one apply the approach used for studies of metabolic allometric scaling in animals to human societies? There is a relationship between the number of people in a strata and their wealth (the greater is the wealth, the less people in a stratum). So, instead of mass in case of animals, we may use sequential fractions P of population possessing greater wealth, while the wealth per capita $w=S/P$ in each stratum (where S is a share of the total wealth for a given stratum in percent), substitutes the amount of nutrients, which an individual animal with certain mass consume. In this study, we will measure both S and P in percent. Such an approach has an advantage that it does not require knowing absolute wealth in money values. However, if wealth or income in monetary values are known, then these numbers can be used in the same way. Later, we will illustrate the last approach too.

Certainly, instead of wealth one can analyze income, which we will also consider, and other population characteristics; the proposed approach in this regard is more general than just for the description of wealth distribution.

A note about terminology. It would be tempting to use the term “allometric exponent” in this study, but the term is reserved for biological objects. So, we will use the term “a slope of regression line” or “a regression slope” for short, which in our case will be analogous to allometric exponents.

Fig. 2. Wealth distribution in the US in 2016 for the equal returns model from [4], depending on population strata in logarithmic coordinates. Solid line - wealth distribution; dashed line - regression line for points 2-4 (counted from right to left, i. e. from 10% to 0.1%). Percent numbers in bold on the graph show size of population's ranges. Values d1 and d7 denote distance from points 1 and 7 to the regression line. Axis x shows logarithm of lower boundary of the range measured in percent.

Fig. 3. Same as on Fig. 2 for wealth distribution calculated based on the baseline model from [4].

Figs. 2 and 3 present graphs of wealth distribution on the basis of data from work [4], for the baseline and equal returns calculation models. (Note that these models produce the lowest share of wealth owned by the richest compared to other studies.) Graphs show noticeable difference between the models, and which specific features of wealth distribution each model accentuates (or suppresses) more. Such, the equal returns model is less sensitive to increasing growth of wealth of the wealthiest stratum compared to the baseline model, and other known to the author similar data. Unlike in Fig. 1 for animals, the slope is negative, but this is a matter of choosing independent variable. For our purposes, the algebraic sign is irrelevant, since we are interested in absolute value of the slope. Table 2 presents original data and calculated parameters. As it was mentioned already, depending on the methodology, results of wealth calculations from various sources can differ for the top group 0.1% as much as several percent of the wealth of the entire population. It is not impossible that some bias might influence such calculations, since these are not the low income people who finance such studies.

It would be interesting to see dynamics of wealth and income distribution over time, especially in the last decade, but the author could not find such consistent data. Still, some interesting results were discovered.

The graphs both on Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 have close to a straight line pieces in the middle of the curves (from point 2 to point 4, which correspond to the range of 10-0.1%). The slopes of the regression curves between different points are presented in Tables 3 and 4. Similar to allometric exponents for living creatures, the values of regression slopes are also important parameters reflecting on the nature of underlying mechanisms defining distribution of wealth and income between and inside different wealth strata of population. The said about the importance of slope values of regression lines is rather a hypothesis at the moment, but it's a credible one. As we can see from Table 4, for the middle part of the graph the average value of regression slopes is (-0.68) for the baseline model, and for the equal returns model it is (-0.737). If we compare their absolute values with allometric exponents for animals, then we could see that these numbers are close to BMR allometric exponents (the ones we should use for comparison purposes; the issue will be discussed later). The equation defining wealth distribution then can be written similar to (1) as $W=a \cdot P^b$. Accordingly, an equation for a regression line is

$$(3) \log(W)=b \cdot \log(P)+\log(a), \text{ where } b < 0.$$

The author did not pose a question about possible existence of straight pieces of regression lines when started this exercise, and it would be difficult to anticipate such an effect. However, once discovered, intuitively, it is not exactly a surprising one. This is the wealth range in which both interacting sides, that is the ones receiving and giving money have some bargaining power, although not necessarily of equal value. (There is also a flow of money to this range from the bottom 90%, which are rather taken from them without bargaining, de facto simply by virtue of imposition. And the same is applied to the flow of money from the bottom 90% to the wealthiest segments.) The receiving side in this range of 10-0.1% apparently has no monopolistic positioning to extract additional profit from customers. Neither they have enough political and governmental influence to secure loosely controlled access to public funds. This situation seemingly provides business environment in which, to a substantial degree, action of market forces and some supply and demand balance between different participants is possible.

In here, we can observe close similarity with distribution of nutritional resources in animal world. In both instances, we see largely independent and isolated actions of all participants directed to acquisition of resources from the common pool, which is a common habitat. In this sense, we can consider such actions as random. Each participant has the *same* possibility, potential to access resources they need. To get these resources, participants exercise methods of acquisition based on principles of about the same level of efficiency. For instance, a bigger animal catches its prey using *chasing*, but a

smaller animal also *chases* its prey. Or, in the world of unicellular organisms, nutrient acquisition is done through the surface both in small and big organisms. The variations in efficiency of different methods are rather *quantitative* than qualitative. Such, a bigger animal can develop higher speed than the smaller animal; *Amoeba* uses endocytosis, swallowing whole smaller organisms. (However, buffaloes do not install fences to monopolize their pastures to gain monopolistic advantage, neither *Amoeba* prohibits *B. subtilis* to reside in a nearby space.) At the same time, *Amoebas* cannot consume too many resources, to the extent that deprives smaller organisms nutrients for sufficient reproduction, because in this case smaller organisms won't reproduce in sufficient quantities, and so *Amoebas* themselves will starve, and eventually the entire food chain will be destroyed.

A similar picture can be seen in a wide range of sizes of businesses and professional services, which all have principally the same potential to access the same resources, and use business methods of qualitatively about the same level of efficiency. However, if some business acquires *qualitative* advantage, say through newly invented technology or due to government connections, it begins taking disproportionately (to its size) greater share of resources, thus jeopardizing acquisition of resources by other businesses. The rearrangement of the previous scheme of distribution of resources occurs. Other businesses begin acquiring less resources, which in turn sets a chain of the following redistributions, in which some businesses can bankrupt. But in a stable, balanced state such a business environment in its main distribution characteristics much resembles natural food chains. And (some conditions applied) it should.

Table 2. Wealth distribution in the US in 2016 [4]. Data used for calculation of regression slopes for wealth and drawing graphs on Figs. 2 and 3. B - Baseline model; ER - Equal Returns model.

Population's ranges, from the bottom, %	Size P of population's ranges, %	log(low range's boundary) x axis	B Relative wealth per capita (S/P)	B Share S of total wealth for a range, %	B log(wealth per capita) y axis	ER Share S of total wealth for a range, %	ER Relative wealth per capita (S/P)	ER log(wealth per capita), ER, y axis
100-10	90	2	0.35	31.4	-0.46	26.7	0.3	-0.52
10-1	9	1	3.88	34.9	0.59	34.4	3.82	0.582
1-0.1	0.9	0	20.00	18	1.30	18.5	20.56	1.313
0.1-0.01	0.09	-1	95.56	8.6	1.98	9.8	108.9	2.037
0.01-0.001	0.09	-2	433.33	3.9	2.64	5.5	611	2.786
0.001-0.00001	0.00099	-3	1717.17	1.7	3.23	3.6	4000	3.602
>0.00001	0.00001	-5	150000.00	1.5	5.18	1.5	150000	5.176

Table 3. Values of regression slopes and intercepts for the graphs of wealth distribution on Figs. 2 and 3. Data for the US, 2016.

Points' range	b, baseline	b, equal returns	c, baseline	c, equal returns
1-7	-0.764	-0.793	1.192	1.233
2-4	-0.696	-0.727	1.29	1.311
2-6	-0.663	-0.751	1.285	1.313
2-5	-0.682	-0.734	1.285	1.313
6-7	-0.971	-0.787	0.323	1.241
Average	-0.755	-0.758		

Table 4. Values of regression slopes for the middle part of graphs of wealth distribution on Figs. 2 and 3. Data for the US, 2016.

Points' range	b, baseline	b, equal returns
2-4	-0.696	-0.727
2-6	-0.663	-0.751
2-5	-0.682	-0.734
Average	-0.680	-0.737

Characterization of logarithmic wealth distribution curves

Now we can introduce some parameters, which could characterize the presented graphs and the phenomenon they describe. We will use as a reference the regression line for the middle parts of curves, which can be well approximated by straight lines. In our case, these are regression lines for points 2-4, whose coefficients b and c are shown in Table 3 (regression line through points 2-4). If we look at Figs. 2 and 3, the points corresponding to wealth of the bottom 90% of population are located *below* the regression lines, at a distance d_1 , while the points corresponding to the wealthiest 0.01% are located *above* the regression line; for the point 7 - at a distance d_7 . Although 0.01% is a small share of population, it possesses 10.6% of wealth according to the equal returns model, and 7.1% according to the baseline model, versus accordingly 26.7% and 31.4% for the bottom 90% of population (Table 2). So, the fractions of wealth we consider are of the same order of magnitude.

We will base such a comparison of wealth for these two segments using the actual wealth values W from Table 2, versus the values of wealth W_r for the same points defined by the regression lines, that is for the points 1 and 7. Then, say for the point 1, using equation (3), we can write $\log(W_r1)=b*\log(P1)+c1$. Here, number 1 is the point on Figs. 2 and 3 corresponding to the bottom 90% of population. Substituting values of regression slope b and intercept c from Table 3 (line 2-4) for the baseline model, we find: $\log(W_r1)=(-0.696)*\log(100)+1.29=(-0.102)$. Then, $W_r1=10^{(-0.102)}=0.79$. Thus we can find the ratio R_{w1} of the real wealth W_1 to the hypothetical wealth W_r1 , defined by the regression line, as $R_{w1}=0.35/0.79=0.44$, so that $W_1=0.44*W_r1$. This means that the real wealth of the bottom 90% of population comprises only 44% of the wealth this segment should have to be located on

the regression line, which, based on analogy with the animal world, would provide decent life and opportunities for self-realization and sustainable reproduction for the population from this segment, as well as social and economic stability for the entire society. Is such an assumption true or not, can be tested empirically considering different countries and comparing quality of life for the entire populations. Of course, different subsegments of population within this large 90% segment have different wealth, but we do not have more detailed data. This consideration will be demonstrated later, when we consider distribution of world income and wealth in 2021, for which there are data for the bottom 50% and the next 40% segments.

Similarly, we can calculate the same ratio of the real wealth to the wealth defined by a regression line (regression ratio for short) Rw_7 for the wealthiest segment at point 7, using data for the baseline model. In this case, we obtain $W_7=1.7*Wr_7$. In other words, the real wealth of the richest comprises 170% of the wealth defined for them by the regression line.

We can also introduce another parameter characterizing wealth disparity between the bottom 90% and the wealthiest segment as $Dw(1,7)=Rw_1/Rw_7=0.26$, that is as the ratio of regression ratios for the appropriate points. Since such a parameter can be used for comparison of different combinations of segments (associated with point numbers here), we can denote the wealth disparity as $Dw_{90}(1,7)$ for clarity. Such a notation includes the bottom reference base (90%), and the compared segments of population denoted by point numbers, i. e. (1,7) in our example. (Certainly, instead of point numbers values of population ranges in percent can be used in notations.) Table 5 presents values of regression ratios and the wealth disparity coefficients both for the baseline and equal returns models.

Of course, the boundaries of population segments can be of arbitrary value. In our case the percentage ranges were defined by available data.

The range of values of the wealth disparity coefficient Dw is $[0, 1]$ when the points for the richer are on or above the regression line, and the points for the wealth of the bottom segment are on or below the regression line. When the points are on the regression line, $Dw=1$. When the bottom segment has no wealth at all, $Dw=0$. So, the obtained value of 0.26 with regard to interpretation and assessment of wealth of the bottom 90% is quite low, which says about high wealth disparity between the bottom 90% of population and the richest class.

Table 5. Parameters characterizing disparity in wealth per capita of the bottom (90%, point 1 in Figs. 2 and 3), and the highest (0.00001%, point 7) wealth groups, using regression line between points 2-4 (10 - 0.1%). Wealth disparity coefficients $Dw_{90}(1,7)$ are in bold. Regression line ratios Rw are in columns 3 and 4.

1	2	3	4	5
Model (points 2-4, i. e. 90 - 0.1%)	$b; c$	$Rw_1 = W_1/Wr_1$	$Rw_7 = W_7/Wr_7$	$Dw_{90}(1,7) = Rw_1/Rw_7$
Baseline	-0.696; 1.29	0.44	1.7	0.26
Equal returns,	-0.727; 1.311	0.42	1.77	0.24

Hypothetically, the wealth disparity coefficient between the poorest and the richest can be greater than one if $Rw_1 > Rw_7$. However, in practical terms, this is an unlikely situation, for which to happen a significant, if not radical, *qualitative* change of a socio-economic system is needed. Still, even in such a

situation the wealth disparity coefficient remains useful for comparison of a calculated number with a value of one. Also, in this case additional parameters can be used, such as, for instance, regression slopes adjacent to considered population segments.

The issue we did not discuss so far, is how to choose sizes of compared population ranges. One approach can be choosing equal ranges of population, say 0.1%. Then one can fix the the upper stratum, and move the interval of 0.1% though the bottom strata of population, thus creating some sort of moving average for a wealth disparity coefficient depending on the value of the low boundary of the moving interval (in percent of population). This way one can obtain a graph showing dynamics of wealth disparity across the chosen lower population strata.

Another approach can be using strata of population with about equal wealth. Combination of both approaches can be used. Both approaches should provide useful results.

Generally, the proposed approach has sufficient number of degrees of freedom to objectively and accurately describe specific features of wide variety of wealth distributions, as well as distributions of other economic, and not only of economic kind, parameters.

The last note of this section pays attention to convenience and universality of the proposed approach for calculations. As a wealth or income measure, we can use either relative or absolute values; the value of introduced parameters will be the same. We can prove this using equation (3) and definition of the straight line's slope b , namely that $b=(\log(W2)-\log(W1))/(\log(P2)-\log(P1))$. Suppose $W1$ and $W2$ are relative values of wealth, and we want instead to use dollar amount $D1$ and $D2$, which are related to $W1$ and $W2$ as $D1=k*W1$, $D2=k*W2$. Substituting these values into the above formulas, one eventually obtains the same expression:

$$b=(\log(k*W2)-\log(k*W1))/(\log(P2)-\log(P1))=$$

$$(\log(k)+\log(W2)-\log(k)-\log(W1))/(\log(P2)-\log(P1))=$$

$$(\log(W2)-\log(W1))/(\log(P2)-\log(P1)),$$

Similarly, for the regression ratio, say for $Rw1$, we have $Rw1=(Wr1-W1)/Wr1$. If we decide to use the dollar amounts $k*Wr1$ and $kW1$, $Rw1=(k*Wr1-k*W1)/(k*Wr1)=(Wr1-W1)/Wr1$, that is the same original value. Obviously, the same is true for the wealth disparity coefficient.

We have no similar data for later years. However, distribution of wealth in 2024, with a smallest top range of 0.1% [7], presented in logarithmic coordinates, shows that inequality increased since 2016, if we assume that both calculation methodologies produce adequate to the real situation data. According to the data from this report, low 90% went down (the slope in absolute values increased from 1.102 to 1.52), while the top 0.1% went up (from 0.784 to 0.902, which is a substantial increase in logarithmic scale). Still, these result is a matter of validity of input data.

Example of distribution of world income and wealth in 2021

Here we analyze another set of data. There will be the following additions to the previous analysis. (a) We consider not only wealth, but also income distribution. (b) Instead of a single segment of population 90% we studied previously, now we have data for the bottom 50%, and for the next 40% population segments. (c) Previously, we used for identification of percentage ranges the values of low boundaries. Now, in addition, we will also identify intervals by middle values of ranges and will study, how this change affects the results. It turned out that not much, which will be demonstrated by appropriate data in a table format. Regarding the graphs of distributions with middle values, they are nearly identical to the graphs identifying range by lower boundaries, and so they are not presented here. (d) We will consider two sets of points for drawing regression lines, namely 2-4 (50%-0.1% interval) and 3-4

(10%-0.1%, as previously). (e) We will use not the relative wealth for calculations, but the actual money in euros.

Fig. 4 presents graphs for income and wealth distribution depending on the population strata in percent, based on data from “World inequality report 2021” [6]. Regression line in Fig. 4 is drawn between points 2-4, which corresponds to the range 50-0.1% (40%, 9%, 0.9% population segments). Data are presented in Table 6. Fig. 5 shows the same data approximated by smooth curves, while the regression line is defined by points 3-4 (10-0.1% range), composed of the population segments of 9% and 0.9%). This is the same interval used for drawing regression lines in the previous section. Original data in [6] include cumulative data for the top 10%, 1%, 0.1%, which were recalculated to find wealth and income corresponding to ranges (10-1%), (1-0.1%).

It is clear that in order for our analysis to make sense, we need to draw a regression line through the middle part of the curve, that is through the points located approximately on a straight line. Otherwise, such a regression line would provide little information about income or wealth disparity. It is possible that the straight part of the distribution curve corresponds to population segments, in which distribution of wealth and income is defined by the same or similar distribution mechanisms and factors, while outside this straight part the distribution is defined by other mechanisms, which suppresses and overwrites mechanisms defining the straight part of the distribution curves.

The regression line in our analysis is of great importance. This is a reference line we measure the wealth and income disparity against. It was previously discussed that the linear character of dependencies between points 2-4 (and to a certain extent between points 2-5) shown on Figs. 2 and 3 is very likely due to uniformity of market mechanisms and factors acting within this population segment, while the mechanisms and factors defining wealth distribution in the bottom 90% and top 0.1% *objectively* have to be different, which could be anticipated even without graphs. Graphs only confirmed this apriori assumption, explicitly showing how greatly the character of these parts of graphs differ from their middle portions. These middle parts present the best reference we can make from what we have. Indeed, this is true (a) from the perspective of analogy with distribution of resources in animal world, which is well described by straight regression lines; (b) from the perspective of similar values of allometric exponents and slopes of regression lines we draw for wealth distribution; (c) but foremost, this is also the fraction of population which has means for decent life in general, enough resources for self-realization and also for reproduction, being able supporting families with several children and providing them opportunities for personal and social development. So, overall, this is a good benchmark to refer to.

Then, based on these considerations, we should draw the regression lines using points 3 and 4, that is for the same range 10-0.1% as for the wealth distribution in the US in 2016, considered in the previous section. Still, we draw regression lines for points 2-4 too, to show how the choice of range for the regression line influences disparity estimations. Results of this comparison are presented in Table 7. As we can see, income disparity in case of regression line for points 2-4 is almost twice as greater than for points 3-4. For the wealth distribution, this difference is five times for the low boundary identification value (0.02 versus 0.10) and four times for the middle of interval (0.03 versus 0.12). Another argument in favor of 3-4 interval for drawing regression lines is that it produces very close values of regression slopes both for the middle points and for the lower boundaries, while the same difference for interval 2-4 is substantially greater, which speaks of lesser stability of estimations based on this interval. Furthermore, the mere values of regression slopes for the 2-4 interval are too big for the wealth distribution to be true, based on previous results (0.87 and 0.903).

Fig. 4. Dependence of wealth distribution on the strata of population in logarithmic scale. Dashed line corresponds to wealth distribution; solid line presents income distribution; a dotted straight regression line is for points 2-4. Values d1 and d5 denote distances from points 1 (50% range) and 5 (0.1% range) to the regression line. Values in percent denote the percentage range corresponding to appropriate population stratum.

Fig. 5. Same as on Fig. 4 for smooth approximation curves. The difference is that the regression line is drawn between points 3-4.

Note the small values of 0.02 and 0.03 for the income and wealth disparities coefficients for the bottom 50% compared to the maximum possible value of one. Also, recall that for the bottom 90% we previously obtained substantially greater values of wealth disparity coefficients, 0.24 and 0.26. This means that the bottom 50% are really at the very bottom, almost touching the minimum possible value of zero. The forty percent segment of population (from 50 to 10%) is also noticeably below the regression lines both for income and wealth distributions.

Table 6. Data from [6] used for calculation of income and wealth regression slopes and graphs in Figs. 4 and 5, and calculated parameters.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Population's shares P, %	Middle of share, %	Share's size, %	log(low bound. L) x axis	log(middle of share M) x axis	Income per capita th. euro	Regr. line, income per capita th. euro	log(income) y axis	Wealth per capita th. euro	Regr. line, wealth per capita th. euro	log(wealth) y axis
100-50	75	50	2.0	1.88	2.8	9.1	0.45	2.9	28	0.46
50-10	30	40	1.7	1.48	16.5	16	1.22	41	58	1.61
10-1	5	9	1.0	0.70	61.2	42	1.79	306	202	2.49
1.0-0.1	0.5	0.9	0.0	-0.30	212.1	146	2.33	1491	991	3.17
0.1-0	0.05	0.1	-1.0	-1.3	1301	696	3.11	14133	8563	4.15

Table 7. Parameters characterizing income and wealth disparity of the bottom 50% and the high 0.1% income and wealth population groups, based on the regression lines between points 3-4 (10 - 0.1%) and between points 2-4 (40 - 0.1%). Income and wealth disparity coefficients $Di50$ and $Dw50$ are in bold.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Model	b; c, Income	$Ri1 = i1/i1r$	$Ri5 = i5/i5r$	$Di50(1,5) = Ri1/Ri5$	b; c, Wealth	$Rw1 = w1/w1r$	$Rw5 = w5/w5r$	$Dw50(1,5) = Rw1/Rw5$
Low, points 3-4	-0.54; 2.327	0.16	1.77	0.09	-0.69; 3.173	0.046	1.95	0.02
Mid, points 3-4	-0.53; 2.164	0.2	1.77	0.11	-0.69; 2.966	0.062	1.95	0.03
Low, points 2-4	-0.645; 2.36	0.24	1.29	0.19	-0.903; 3.24	0.108	1.03	0.10
Mid, points 2-4	-0.62; 2.164	0.28	1.39	0.20	-0.87; 2.967	0.135	1.13	0.12

We considered piece-wise lines on Fig. 4 and a smooth curve on Fig. 5 built on discrete points. Since the value of P, whose logarithm presents x-axis, is continuous, and the change of wealth distribution does not show sharp jumps (at least in the present economical situation) and thus is a rather smooth function too, the actual dependencies of income and wealth distributions are better presented by smooth curves on Fig. 5, although the upturn of the curve almost surely would be much sharper at top segments, if we had more detailed data.

Regarding whether to use the middle points of population ranges or their low boundaries, it is hard to say, since both approaches produce close values of calculated parameters shown in Table 7. (The best answer would be to have a more discrete statistics at the bottom ranges.) The middle point estimation for the bottom segments, given the concave character of a curve at this range, is biased to produce higher values of regression ratios, and consequently is biased to give a greater value of wealth and income disparity coefficients. So, the solution could be some more complicated approach, like using not the middle point, but the one closer to the low boundary, or just to stay with the low boundary.

Note close values of regression slopes obtained for both sets of data for the same 10-0.1% population segment, presented in Tables 5 and 7, namely the values of -0.69 in Table 7 and of -0.696 in Table 5 (for the baseline model, which is generally considered as a more adequate one compared to the equal returns model). A slightly greater regression slope for the US 2016 data might reflect on a somewhat faster acceleration of wealth accumulation in the US, when wealth per capita increases, even five years earlier, than in the world in 2021. It could be, given the scale, agility and preferential treatment of big businesses in the US economy.

Now regarding the smaller in absolute values regression slopes of (-0.53) and (-0.54) for the income distribution from Table 7, for a 3-4 points interval, which are less than in case of wealth distribution. These numbers could be true. However, to be certain, the accounting practices should be considered in this regard too, since in more wealthy groups the actual income could be accounted as wealth increase, like capital gains (which falls into lower tax brackets).

Another perspective from the natural world on wealth distribution in human societies

The difference in nutrient consumption of the biggest (*Amoeba*) and the smallest (*B. subtilis*) unicellular organisms is about 37,000 [1], while the difference in mass is about $3.0 \cdot 10^7$. For land mammals, the difference in metabolic rate is close to 18,800 for the basal metabolic rate (BMR) [2], and is about $3.33 \cdot 10^6$ for the mass difference (Elephant vs Etruscan shrew). Note that the relative differences in consumed resources in both instances are close, despite the fact that we consider very different groups of organisms. Also, we should use rather BMR than MMR (maximal metabolic rate) for multicellular organisms because they spend most of the time at low physical activity. Since metabolic rate closely correlates with amount of consumed nutrients, in case of mammals we may use the same numbers for nutrient consumption. The relationship between the ratios of nutrient consumption N of the biggest and n of the smallest animals, and their masses M and m accordingly, can be derived from equation (1). It is as follows:

$$(4) N/n = (M/m)^b$$

The wealth of low 20% of population is very small, these people live on income [5]. The bottom 10% have value of wealth counted in thousands dollars. Then, for the wealth of \$5,000, the maximum should be $5 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 18,800 = 94 \cdot 10^6$, that is about one hundred million dollars, if we use distribution of nutrients between land mammals as a base. If we use unicellular organisms, then about two times more. Thus, one-two hundred million dollars should be the maximum wealth possession in order for the distribution of wealth in human societies could mimic distribution of resources in animals, that is could be described by a straight line in logarithmic coordinates with a similar slope value. Of course, raising the lower income and wealth would raise their upper boundaries too. However, in here, the total amount of wealth should be accounted for, which we will do later. In fact, the difference in wealth between the richest and the poorest human beings is much greater. Say, one hundred billion wealth W_t

of an individual at the top is greater than the wealth of an individual W_p in the low 50% (USD 2900 [6]) by about $W_t/W_p=34,000,000$ (thirty four million) times. (Compare this number to 18,800 and 37,000 in the animal world.) For the allometric exponent for land mammals from Table 1 this would produce the difference in mass, according to equation (1),

$$(W_t/W_p)^{(1/b)}=(W_t/W_p)^{(1/0.682)}=1.1*10^{11}$$

Assuming the smallest mammal weighs 2 grams, the biggest mammal then should weigh about 220,000 tons (two hundred twenty thousand) in order to mimic distribution of wealth in human societies by distribution of nutrients depending on animal's mass in nature. (In other words, as much as 31,560 big elephants weigh.) Of course, no natural habitat can sustain such a monster, aside from impossibility of biological existence of such a gigantic creature. The humankind can be proud of this achievement, creating an enormous global habitat whose resources are practically uncontrollably exploited by the tiniest group of people. Or can it?

Optimal distributions of income and wealth based on regression lines

Here, we will find dependencies of income and wealth distributions when they are defined by regression lines with slopes corresponding to the middle parts of real dependencies (i. e. to the range 10-0.1% in Figs. 2-5). These values of slopes, as we discussed above, seem optimal from the perspective of providing good quality of life for this prosperous population sector.

The problem is posited as this. We know the total wealth, and we want all this wealth to be distributed among population sectors in a way defined by regression lines with a given slope. So that if we then calculate the total wealth based on regression line's distribution, it should be equal to the original total wealth. The same approach will be used to find an appropriate income distribution.

To achieve this purpose, we use average income and average wealth values from Table 1.1 in work [6], which are accordingly equal to $I_{av}=16,700$ and $W_{av}=72,900$ euros. For convenience, we will do calculations in thousand euros. Then, using (1), we can write the following equation for the average wealth across all population.

$$(5) W_{av} = a * \left(\int_{100}^0 P^b dP \right) / \left(\int_{100}^0 dP \right) = \frac{a * P^{(b+1)} \Big|_{100}^0}{(b+1) P \Big|_{100}^0}$$

from which we can find constant a as

$$a = (W_{av}) / [-100^{(b+1)}] / [-100 * (b+1)]$$

Similar formula should be used to find value of a for income distribution. Substituting regression slopes $b_w=(-0.69)$ for the wealth distribution, and $b_i=(-0.54)$ for income distribution from Table 7, we find $a_w=542$, $a_i=92.36$, where indexes 'w' and 'i' correspond to wealth and income accordingly. Then, we can write:

$$(6) I = a_i * P^{(b_i)},$$

$$(7) W = a_w * P^{(b_w)}$$

These equations are free from particular values of population segments, but define income and wealth for an arbitrary values of P. So, these are differential distributions. For instance, for the lowest income, at 100%, we obtain $I(100)=92.36*100^{(-0.54)}=7.68$ th. euros. However, we deal with distributions for segments of population. In this case, we should use an equation similar to (5), for a population segment defined by boundaries r_1 and r_2 . Then, (5) will be rewritten as follows.

$$(8) \bar{W}_{av} = a * \left(\int_{r_1}^{r_2} P^b dP \right) / \left(\int_{r_1}^{r_2} dP \right) = \frac{a * P^{(b+1)} \Big|_{r_1}^{r_2}}{(b+1) P \Big|_{r_1}^{r_2}}$$

For instance, if we want to find the average income for the bottom 50%, we should use equation (8) with boundaries $r_1=100\%$ and $r_2=50\%$, which will produce the value of 9.12 th euros. Compare this with the actual average income for the bottom 50%, which is 2.8 th euros, that is 3.25 times less. It is not unrealistic to increase the income of low bottom as much, but not in the most modern socioeconomic systems. For the value of 0.1% of differential income we accordingly obtain 320.2 th euro, and the average value of 696.2 th euro for the top segment of 0.1%. Income and wealth amounts per capita corresponding to regression lines with aforementioned slopes are presented in Table 6 in columns 7 and 10 in bold, beside the columns 6 and 9 for the real income and wealth.

A note with regard to usage of formula (8). Mathematically, since $b < 0$, when P goes to zero (i. e. at top segments), both differential income I and wealth W in (6) and (7), as well as \bar{W}_{av} in (8) go to infinity. That would mean that after a certain small value of P equation (8) starts calculating the average wealth for a population segment consisting of a fraction of one person, which does not make sense. The practical approach can be as follows. Suppose we want to know the maximum average wealth for a group of 1000 (10^3) people, in a country with population one hundred million (10^8). Then this group comprises $(10^3):(10^8)=10^{(-5)}$ fraction of the population, or $(10^{(-5)})*(10^2)=0.001\%$. Substituting this value into (8), we obtain $\bar{W}_{av}=205$ ml for the regression slope of (-0.69) corresponding to the middle part of the curve presenting real wealth distribution in a world in 2021. Coincidentally, about the same number we found previously based on different considerations.

How far from reality?

In this study, a benchmark for a fair inequality, so to say, was proposed and analyzed from different perspectives for two sets of data. Previously, it was discussed that it is justified referring to introduced regression lines, analogous to metabolic allometric scaling in nature, for the purpose of studies of specifics of income and wealth distribution in human societies. It was indicated that the middle parts of wealth and income distribution curves drawn in logarithmic scale, and corresponding to prosperous, but not very rich segments of population, are indeed well approximated by straight lines, which is clearly seen on Figs. 2-5 for both data sets. Even more surprising fact is that the values of regression slopes in this range of population are close to values of slopes of analogous regression lines for animals (allometric exponents). Based on experience of modeling different natural phenomena and technological processes, and generalizations derived from results of these studies, such similarity, observed in both sets of data, cannot be a coincidence. This rather means that similar general level mechanisms affect distribution of resources both in animal world and in this segment of human societies. Analogously to the animal world, such a distribution of wealth and income should provide stability and sustainability for all people in this segment of population (and it indeed does).

The reasons for such an effect were discussed in more detail previously. It was remarked that economic relations in this segment are characterized by (a) availability of certain bargaining power for all interacting parties, although to a different extent, which could be one of the possible possible

reasons for appearance of distributions similar to the ones existing in nature. The next factor (b) is about equal potential for all participants to access resources of a habitat, and the third one (c) is usage of methods for resource acquisition of about equal efficiency. So, the proposed regression lines have connection with real phenomenon, namely with distribution of important economic characteristics - of income and wealth.

Then, the next question arises. Is the distribution described by regression lines optimal from the perspective of overall well-being of human societies, considered on different scales? (Same as distribution of nutritional resources can be optimal for habitats of different size.) Certainly, criteria of well being can be different, and even their application can be biased, as is the case with countries subsidizing rating agencies. However, still there is an element of truth in such ratings. If one takes distribution of wealth and income in countries with good overall standard of living, then these distributions will be *closer* to a regression line, and their income and wealth disparity coefficients will be closer to one, than in case of countries with worse well being measurements. Thus, the idea using regression lines and the introduced ratios R_w , R_i and disparity coefficients D_w , D_i for such estimation purposes is supported by available data, despite a certain ambiguity of this data. This ambiguity appears because of different methodologies used for calculation of wealth and income in different population strata, insufficient or distorted input data, certain biases of people, conducting such studies - for different reasons, etc. There are also objective reasons making accounting for income and wealth difficult. For instance, there can be some public spending indirectly increasing the actual income in all groups, improving their quality of life. How to properly account for a well developed infrastructure, cheap commuting fares, government funded child care? These could be intricate subjects on their own, which could affect income and wealth distributions. On the other hand, it's understandable that in most countries these will be inputs rather of the second order of magnitude.

What can we learn from the obtained results?

The second issue to be raised, besides the validation of the proposed method for analysis of income and wealth distribution, is its practical applications, which can be very many. For now, we restrict ourselves with observation of facts, which are known already from other sources, but which received solid confirmation by obtained results.

The first one is a well known fact of accelerating accumulation of wealth and income in the richest segments. Graphs on Figs. 2-5, and related data in Tables 2, 5, 6 and 7 expose this phenomenon very clearly, whatever data for wealth distribution is used. The curves for wealth and income per capita beginning about 0.01% and the following segments climb steeper and steeper above the regression line when the wealth and income per capita increase. Bending the curve upward this way in logarithmic scale required very fast increase indeed. On the other hand, the bottom segments of income and wealth distribution are located well below the regression line, and the poorer people are, the steeper is the decline. Such a behavior of distribution curves means nothing but a very compelling evidence of a well organized and maintained machinery pumping resources from the bottom 90% to the wealthy segments. If we take a look at columns 6, 7 and 9, 10 in Table 6, we can see that both income and wealth per capita begin exceeding values defined by regression lines at about 10% segment. This and all segments above pump resources from the bottom 90%, but the wealthiest pump disproportionately more.

However, if one thinks for a moment, it could not be otherwise. The richest take more for the following reasons. First, the present socioeconomic system, of which political system is an inherent component, is designed in such a way that money buy power. More money buy and wield more social, economic and political power, which is used to suck more and more resources pretty much from

everybody and everything else. And the less power particular segments of population have, the more resources are taken from them, since they are deprived ability, lawfully and otherwise, to resist such economic policies, which some call “legalized robbery”. “Lawfully”, because the wealthiest and belonging to them or bought by them governments have enough power to legitimize and impose on society as laws the rules enforcing and protecting interests of riches. Besides this already very efficient instrument of economic coercion of the bottom 90% of population, the richest have many other efficient means to further secure their advantageous economical, social and political position.

The second important component of the toolset for extraction resources from the rest of population and protecting its possession by riches is propaganda, which includes all sorts of myths, stories, news, brain washing narratives, public opinion manipulation, and alike. In this, the riches are very well positioned owning or controlling media, social platforms, video material, film production and what not. This very powerful information producing machine creates and distributes tailored to needs of riches propagandistic stamps and stereotypical thinking patterns, embeds and then maintains them in peoples’ conscious and subconscious minds, and thus controls and manages population’s views, beliefs, preferences, and eventually actions; as well as inactions.

Peoples’ minds in general are very malleable entities, which can be formed in almost any imaginable fashion just by supplying an adjusted for a particular purpose input information, targeting the appropriate brain regions to excite required emotions, to sow suspicion and distrust, or, vice versa, hope and trustfulness. The ability to intercept and analyze such manipulative information can be trained, some, but not many, people have such a gift from birth, but majority of people have neither conditions, nor knowledge and level of intellectual development and training to counteract such massive and omnipresent brain washing informational torrents. This is the reality we have, which would be difficult to change.

The third cornerstone of the pump house the riches erected and furnished with efficient equipment, is availability of resources and access to them, which allowed creating a well developed network of interconnected (supposedly private) organizations and institutions, which promote, propagate and implement wide range of interests of rich people. Such networks and their hubs are efficiently using governing national bodies, as well as international organizations. The influence of these non-governmental organizations at national and international levels could be enormously powerful, when a handful of self-elected people could appoint presidents, prime ministers and other high rank officials of countries, define economical and political policies of big states through their agents, set paths for the whole regions and unions of states. For instance, such a situation is well illustrated by subjugated policies of European Union and of many other countries.

Of course, the said would be immediately branded as a “conspiracy theory”, but the thing is that such activities are presently so much on the surface, that even elementary common sense is sufficient to notice such “conspiracies”. It usually takes little effort to decipher, who controls this or that newly “elected” official. And if not, the career path usually reveals, at which point he/she was sworn to a servitude and to whom. Even more so that many people who manage world affairs through these unofficial bodies cannot resist vanity to show how powerful they are, and in one way or another expose such their “achievements” to the public. The author very rarely hears news and media narratives, but even through this minuscule information the described arrangement of the present world governance manifests itself often almost in the open, especially in the last couple years.

The forth foundation of the power of riches is a creation of environment, in which wealth possession became a sacred institution and the measure of all worthy virtues humans could possess. Wealth as such is so much cherished and praised by different means, that in a view of many people it became like a highly desirable virtue, a valor, which everybody should value, respect, and if able, aim for it. And that the wealth is such a precious thing, that its attainment justifies pretty much almost any

means. Examples of rich scammers and criminals escaping punishment are so numerous, that it became a common anecdotal knowledge long time ago. Unfortunately, such a mentality of valuing wealth just for its sake penetrated into pores of society at all levels, thus destroying its morality. And that comes in addition to degradation of societal morality done by exploitation and deprivation of majority of population by modern socioeconomic systems. People are viewed as pawns, subjects for exploitation not only by riches, but also by all levels of government, businesses, and pretty much by every body, which can exercise even a minor authority over people, since degraded morality and thus instilled individualism atomizes society, makes everybody an enemy, a competitor for resources, down to the very bottom of a social ladder.

Capitalistic *economic* relationships, meaning the moving and using of capital that serves material production or otherwise useful for society purposes, could be an efficient economic tool. However, it should not dominate, should not roll down the whole society for the only purpose to get more and more profits for few, by *all* means, thus destroying and disfiguring all other societal institutions, including governmental ones, and tramping down other alternative economic approaches. Capitalism in its present form, by and large, subjugated the whole society to serve the riches. It is not an optimum. It's extremism in much inhuman form. Economy, ideology, politics should serve *all* people, for the society to be functional, stable and prosperous. Sure enough, the real picture is more complicated, but the described mechanism is a backbone structure, a framework, on which the society as a whole functions.

Thus, the above considerations are very much in sync with the results of this study, which discovered accelerated accumulation of wealth in the richest part of the wealth spectrum. This wealth comes mostly from the bottom 90% of population, but statistically the situation looks more tricky, and some studies claim that the income in some lower income strata increased. On the other hand, the economic situation in the bottom 90% in the majority of western countries is dire. Governmental statistical reports can say anything, but the shelves of grocery stores present much more reliable data. Say, within a year several shelves with fresh fruits and vegetables, available previously, in many stores in Scotland and England contracted to one-two, while the freed space was filled with cheaper frozen food and other cheaper stuff. The reason is obvious - people just cannot afford more expensive fresh fruits and vegetables. We won't elaborate on that, but the indicators of the real economic situation of the bottom segments of population are numerous indeed.

Methods by which the wealthiest realize their strategic advantages

Above we discussed what strategic advantages riches created for themselves to pump wealth from lower income and wealth groups to their coffers. Here, we will list the main "technical" instruments and mechanisms for implementing this workflow. However, first we should make few notes about the economic environment, which much facilitates extraction of resources from the bottom population segments on a worldwide scale, which comprise about ninety percent or so.

As it was said previously, and this is true with regard to both animals' food webs and human societies, generally, the greater is a habitat, the greater is amount of resources it contains, and so the more resources can be extracted from it. This is one of the main sources of insatiable desire of riches to enlarge the habitats, which resources they could exploit (wars, colonization are also about larger habitats and their control). The parallel with animal world might surprise some people, but the resemblance is nonetheless almost obvious. And this is where the modern form of money comes to the scene as one of the best tools for conquering and annexing new habitats. How much can one increase material production? Building two, three, five more factories, enlarge existing ones? And this is probably it. The consumption of material goods is limited, their production needs resources, manufacturing process needs workforce, logistics, organization, and many other things. It's

complicated, and complexity grows disproportionately faster than size increases. Mistakes in a material world are costly. The feedback from the real world is prompt and unforgiving, and it is difficult to overwrite.

Another story with the modern money. Money is an idea, an abstraction. Originated as an equivalent of worth, in silver or gold, it was separated, at the beginning of 20-s century, from its material content and became a *pure abstraction*, which from now on could operate on its own, in a way much different from real things it originated on the basis of. However, although deprived of material content, it was, both forcefully and slyly, imposed on societies, and eventually tied to the worth of real things in confused societal consciousness. Then, despite rebellions and protests, this *qualitatively new* abstraction of money, whose nature changed drastically once it was separated from the material world, entangled and subdued economies of countries and of the whole world, as well as of people's personal lives, with strong omnipresent financial webs. From the *means, instrument* serving the world of real things, money became a self-sufficient entity to which the world of real things, to a substantial degree, became a servant; money started affecting and managing, often to a crooked will, the world of real things. When detached from the real world abstractions begin interfering into processes of making decisions, the worldview becomes confused, inadequate and chaotic, and such also become the thoughts, decisions and actions, thus introducing a great deal of chaos into a real world.

The money as just a name. The morphing of this pure abstraction into self-sufficient entity, entangling pretty much an entire globe by its web, and capable affecting it in a desirable for the money owners way, much changed the nature of planetary socioeconomic life, greatly enlarged the habitat, and consequently the amount of resources, the money owners gained access to and could exploit. As it always happens with abstract notions, wealth acquisition as an idea has many features of a game, intermixed with real life. A bad combination indeed, as history proved many times, when, say, some ideology begins affecting peoples' decisions and actions. As in any game, wealth acquisition values symbols, tokens detached from reality, but the problem is that its participants play with real lives, real sufferings, real desperation and tragedies. However, in a big game of wealth and power that real life does not matter. Existence of such publications as Forbes is an undeniable proof of that - once stripped of clothes, this is a gaming report, to whose *symbolic, abstract* prizes lives of the majority of population to be sacrificed. (Hundred twenty meters yachts, billions cost vocational properties in French Riviera, eighty million price tag for a senseless painting, which in turn is a token of another game - in art, first and foremost are *symbols, tokens* in the game that plays with real things.) Too bad that it is just gambling that so much influences life of people and societies, because gambling never ends well.

Usury. Once the money became a pure abstraction, they can be handled by different rules than material things, because abstractions have practically unlimited number of degrees of freedom. One can built abstraction on abstraction on abstraction endlessly. Errors can be transferred to different regions and a burden of consequences can be laid on people which had no relation to those errors. More and more invented financial instruments prove this without doubt. Usury is the ancient and still one of the most powerful (while also one the most devilish) instruments of wealth extraction from people. In fact, this is a cornerstone of the western financial and exploitation system. Remove this support, and the whole system will break. Even in the simplest case, one can just type in the computer a number with many zeros on the right, which are declared to be the money, and then lend this money to some generalized Argentina's government at a hefty usury rate, while at the same time securing a default on lent debt. And then the lender grabs *real* assets instead of typed in the computer numbers. This new money, of which only the name remained from the thing once conceived in the past of humankind as an

equivalent of worth, is an absolutely amazing thing for enriching few, and depriving the rest. It is usury that makes growth of GDP such a central thing for many governments, since governments are forced or incentivized to borrow money, often in a la Argentina fashion, and then to pay interest, for which the GDP is the main source for paying (for certain reasons currency emissions are tied to GDP growth in many countries, unless the country has ability selling its money worldwide with little restrictions - for some time though, since good times eventually always end). Usury is one of the important instruments that drives increase of the money amount and enforces its supply.

People used to think that financial systems cannot work without usury. Actually, easily. But for that the socioeconomic system should be different. Recall how seriously many economists were talking about growing debt of provincial governments in China, predicting a spectacular crash. People, familiar with financial systems of countries in which monetary policy is in the hands of central governments caring about *real* economy and prosperity of their countries, would not even bother with such question. To these people it was obvious that all these debts would be just forgiven at some point. As it happened. Did this any harm to Chinese economy? No. Recall what happened to Greece in about the same situation. And in what state is the Greece's economy and its population now? Usury is a sacred cow only in countries governed by riches, much through the financial system. In such countries the *real* economy serves financial systems designed to extract the money for the rich. In China and similarly caring about real economies and its populations countries, at least a bit, as this example shows, the *financial* system serves the real economy.

Much can be said about intricate and direct usury workings and tricks, but we will restrict ourselves to a remark about usury as an important "technical" instrument for pumping income and wealth from the bottom ninety or so percent of population to the richest segments. (And thus depriving those bottom segments of population of decent living, better health, perspectives, hopes, intellects, families, children and everything else that could be available if that wealth was not taken away from them.)

Inflation is another instrument in the pump house, that also works hard to secure growth of prosperity of the wealthiest and deprivation of the rest. Inflation is known for many centuries. However, when the money were tied to the real assets, it just fluctuated around the same average value for many centuries. The situation drastically changed at the beginning of 20-s century, when the processes of uncoupling the money and the real assets began. Since then inflation grows continuously, and this growth will not stop, unless the system is changed. In fact, inflation is one of the important foundations of the western financial systems. Due to usury and currency emissions, which many countries practice not exactly in a discreet way (the thing also known by different soothing and misleading names, like quantitative easing), the amount of money increases. There are other factors contributing the same phenomenon, but for our purposes this is not critical.

Causes of inflation can be different, but the inflation as a tool is used about the same way to extract worth from the bottom segments of population. A vivid recent example could be pandemic and after-pandemic years, when most of the population at the bottom segments were robbed of their incomes and small possessions, if any, through inflation. During pandemic, the interest was lowered, while the money supply was plentiful (many governments borrowed money and put them into circulation by different means and through different streams, including corruption schemes.) At the same time, supply chains were distorted, some were broken, which significantly decreased supply volume and created certain deficit of goods (which is by itself also causes inflation). Closure of small and middle businesses (for no sound reasons actually), while leaving open only happy big retailers, created excellent conditions for breeding monopolistic business environment, in which monopolists, as they always do, were increasing prices by leaps and bounds on a weekly basis. The situation was

sustainable, since enough people had some reserves, plus many were receiving government's pandemic subsidies. So, big retailers did not have problems selling goods at rather exorbitant prices. Remote work, mandated in many companies, and the usual fear crowds experience during pandemics, created stimulus to buy housing outside the big cities. Coupled with low interest rate and limited supply, this led to skyrocketed housing prices in urban areas surrounding big cities, tens and more percent (some reports cite two-fold increase in many areas in Canada, for instance). In addition, in some countries, like Canada, enormous migrant inflow during this period exacerbated many problems, housing availability and housing prices including.

Once after-pandemic business activity started resuming, interest rates were pushed up, making borrowing more expensive. Many supply chains were not restored though. At the same time, population's reserves were depleted soon after pandemic ended, while prices on everything continued to increase fast. It is not only cycling inter-dependencies, like higher gasoline prices pulled up transport expenses, increasing costs of building materials increased construction costs, etc., but also much enforced and cemented during pandemic monopolistic position of big companies, which in no way wanted to lose such an enormous advantage, contributed to continued growth of prices. Besides, many small and even some middle businesses did not survive pandemic, whose market share went to big monopolistic companies as well, and that weakened competition too. Thus, the whole price net, so to say, was much lifted up compared to the incomes and savings of the most segments of population. Even if incomes in some these segments somewhat increased in absolute numbers (the statistics on this account is conflicting though, but let it be), in relative values, compared to the pre-pandemic times, the real worth of income and assets reduced significantly. Statistics, understandably, does not provide real numbers on this account. My subjective estimations give the drop to 40-65% of pre-pandemic wealth and income most people did have, depending on what set of goods and services to consider. At the same time, the real wealth and income of the top 0.01% increased tens of percent on average, as many sources report. It is obvious, that this increase was fed by the wealth and income taken from the bottom 90% of population. So, this is an example of how inflation helped the riches to strip off wealth and income the bottom 90% and to move those money to the higher segments in case of pandemic and after-pandemic years.

However, in a similar way it works in more stable times, creating more wealth for the riches and reducing wealth and income for the bottom segments. Investing and gambling in financial markets is often presented to general public as a sure means to save assets from inflation, and even enriching themselves. But this is a hoax for the overwhelming majority of people, in all aspects, a suggestion to go gambling with an opponent who controls the game and can add as many aces into a deck of cards as he/she wishes. It is not that the idea of investing is wrong. Resources should have ability to move, and in this sense monetary system could provide flexibility. The problem is that besides carrying some useful functions, the whole system was rigged for speculation and market manipulation to essentially extract resources from the bottom segments of population and elsewhere. It is that the entire system is deeply flawed if it allows to so many people, engaged in financial speculation and other financial activity, to produce nothing of material content or something that could benefit material content, while consuming so much material resources made by others. Inflation is always an exciting opportunity for the rich and curse for the people from bottom segments. Besides, this financial gambling introduces a great deal of chaos and uncertainty in societal life, distracts lots of resources for unproductive use. What a great amount of energy and time is spent by so many people, trying to profit on financial markets instead of doing something *useful* - for themselves and society (and through this societal good benefiting themselves as well).

Life (and for that sake nothing in nature) cannot be purely deterministic, it always includes a random component. But there is an optimal ratio of stability and randomness, which benefits society

the most. In present capitalistic societies, the randomness, often to the degree of a chaos, prevails much beyond this optimum. Constructive moving forward, societal progress (in a good meaning) requires certain *stability*, at all levels of life, but presently it is absent. And it will be this way until capitalism wholly owns the world, but not presents just one of the many economic mechanisms, balanced by numerous *rational* regulations and mechanisms guarding the good for the whole society.

Monopolism. Monopolistic capitalism, in the form of big companies, explicit or implicit cartels is probably not the subject to be discussed in detail, since everybody has had many chances to see it in action in everyday life. When the company supplying gas for heating in your house is increasing price, had your ever a chance to negotiate its reduction? By the same monopolistic, and also hard pressing token, governments of all levels charge taxes and frequently increase them without explanation why and what for. The rich can and do negotiate taxes, escape to “tax heavens”, register businesses and trusts in offshore zones, and have other numerous options to reduce or entirely escape taxes. The rest is doomed to pay ever increasing taxes and all sorts of levies, while getting less and less in return in public spending, which also favors rich - because rich can buy governments, while those at the bottom 90% cannot. And this easy access to public funds the richest have further increases their wealth.

Education. Controlling education is another excellent instrument for shaping and stamping peoples’ minds in a way favorable to wealthy strata of population. The primary purpose of education is legitimization of the existing socioeconomic system, embedding blind trust, adherence, fidelity and faith to it and its institutions, and associated with them wealthiest part as guardians and saviors of state and its population, and of the whole world, when needed. Education is also the means promoting sick and destructive ideas, including the ones called presently collectively “social engineering”, and whatever other interests riches and their separate groups may conceive. Patriotism is another useful for riches instrument, although it should be transformed from fidelity to a country and its people to fidelity to associated with the country governments and the ruling elites.

Another purpose of education should be providing professional practical knowledge needed to do a particular job, but by no means general education and even more so developing critical thinking - the ruling class considers thinkers dangerous, since they could recognize fundamental flaws and inherent injustice of the present system, and even attempt reorganizing it. In other words, riches see any thinker not servicing them as a potential danger to be neutralized as early as possible, and the education system fulfills this task.

Much more can be said how the education system and the academic environment works for riches and why, and how the role of higher education is quickly transforming, exterminating not only freedom of speech, but the freedom of thought altogether, thus becoming more and more a servant of interests of riches. Money can buy not only power, but intellects as well.

Unemployment, especially the high one, is a sure means to keep salaries low and employees dependent and obedient. This obedience may actually include wider spectrum of duties other than those directly related to work, such as political, moral (or immoral), religious, etc. views and actions. Job is not the right to be secured and guaranteed by a socioeconomic system (as it should), but a benevolence on part of an employer, a gift that can be given or not at will. Of course, the issue is not as simple, it has many aspects, depending on economic situation, as well as counteracting mechanisms and masking decorations, but its essence, its core principles are namely such as described.

Offshoring manufacturing, services and jobs is another invaluable instrument to increase manifold riches’ profits, avoid or significantly reduce taxes, save on workplace safety, and so on. It’s a great tool

indeed. Besides, it has many positive side effects (for riches) in the home country, increasing unemployment, destroying local manufacturing and services, thus lowering standards of living, education, feeling of community cooperation, degrading peoples' intellect and morality, making them more indifferent, insensitive, more foolish and stupid, which in turn facilitates brain washing and manipulation. (There is a minor obstacle though - to a certain degree. Once this degree is exceeded, and it is always eventually exceeded, the reckoning comes, unexpectedly and in a form nobody could anticipate.)

There is much more to say how the wealthiest control and rule the countries and the world. We did not mention wars - hot, cold, and hybrid ones, but they also work very well for enrichment of wealthiest and facilitating control of population. Three years of war in Ukraine and Russia fabulously enriched oligarchs in western countries, Ukraine and Russia. The smokescreen of crumbs from modern philanthropy serves interests of riches very well too, and, in fact, promoting these interests became by and large the sole purpose of such "charities". The wealthiest as a class is not uniform either, with different groups pursuing specific interests, especially in times of elite overproduction, as the author of [8] discovered, but we even did not touch this (and we did not need to for the purpose of this study). Even more so, more and more new instruments to enhance the riches' power and to open new opportunities are invented and deployed. However, the said is sufficient to show that the discovered specifics of wealth and income distribution is not a coincidence, but it has deep, foundational level causes to be namely such and not the other way, promoting and protecting interests of riches and depriving the rest of population. In fact, the system is *internationally designed* to pump wealth and income from the lower ninety and more percent of population to the wealthiest segment.

And so what?

The said above is by no means revelation; this is pretty much common knowledge; one can see exhibitions of action of all the described instruments on a daily basis. Most people either know or "feel by a liver" all these things. However, the grip of riches is strong enough to not allow such opinions to be widely spoken publicly. The whole army of journalists (and now in addition internet trolls) serve this "mission", concocting counter-arguments to any statement touching interests of riches.

Wealth transforms peoples' mentality. I saw this first hand many times. The bigger the wealth, the greater is this transformation, so that eventually a new social class originates. Not for the reasons the wealthiest are trying to promote (which is mostly their original, at birth, exceptionality), for which they go at length to prove this faulty premise. There is nothing special about the wealthy as humans. There is not a single virtuous trait in them which is not widely present in humankind. As the author of [9] says, "Just because someone is in possession of a large amount of money does not mean he/she has something useful to say. In fact it generally means the opposite." And also, "The kind of attention to overt materialism required to elevate someone into the category of billionaire is proportionate to the lack of wisdom such a person exhibits. How else could it be?" Such delirious, destructive for humankind (and destructive for themselves too, as history shows!) ideas, such as launching endless wars, mass migrations, depopulation, which many riches are trying to implement on a large scale, says much about their "wisdom". As Joseph Conrad said in his masterpiece "Heart of Darkness", portraying humanity: "Their talk, however, was the talk of sordid buccaneers: it was reckless without hardihood, greedy without audacity, and cruel without courage; there was not an atom of foresight or serious intention in the whole batch of them, and they did not seem aware these things are wanted for the work of the world." (Much undervalued thought, by the way, because people do not take enough labors to

decipher this message and generalize it.) And the said, unfortunately, is much applicable to the actions, intentions and especially to the “foresight” of the riches.

Wealth is praised so much because the public opinion was shaped by the media, which riches own and control, for admiring wealth. The author of [9] says in this regard: “Wealth is mesmerising. Extreme wealth is intoxicating. And because most of mankind is equally mesmerized by these beasts of Mammon, they find a ready audience wherever they go, whatever they do and say.”

As a *socially* different class, the wealthy act as any predator in a food chain would do, that is they acquire resources. The problem is that in modern human societies this purely animal instinct has no natural restrictions, as animals do in nature. And so this instinct, added with enormous power of artificial instruments, allows this class to suck resources of huge habitats, to the detriment of other inhabitants. Simple as that.

Will they moderate this their innermost instinct? No. It’s surely in a reptilian brain, and maybe partly in the brain of lower mammals, and one can do little to change their behavior (all humans have primordial reptilian brain, brain of lower mammals, and the brain of higher mammals). Human life is driven by instincts, which sometimes are modulated by reason - in some people. It is only the mortal danger, strong instinctive fear, affecting the same reptilian brain, can do the trick. This happened, for instance, when Bolsheviks grabbed the power in Russia in 1917. It took only six weeks to pass laws about 8-hour working day instead of a longer one (previously 10-12 hours) in France and Portugal, while the previous struggle of workers for the same act, which lasted for *decades*, brought nothing. It was the same subconscious *fear* of socialism in the USSR, however primitive that socialistic system was, which much contributed to a better lot of bottom groups of western populations - the phenomenon a renown economist T. Piketty could not find rational explanation for in his book. Fear, Professor Piketty, mainly just irrational animal fear, which in the 30-s triggered *reason* in some people in wealthiest class to share the common wealth more uniformly. They were also taught by calamities of world wars (which they launched in pursuit of more wealth and power). Once that generation has gone, the previous wealth distribution has had to return back, because the next generation did not experience that fear, and their reptilian brain’s instinct was not checked.

After the Second World War, one more reason appeared - the need to buy populations’ loyalty to get their support for an uncompromising fight with a mortal enemy - a danger of socialism as a mere idea, associated that time with the USSR. (Socialist countries were mortal enemies for capitalists by *only* their mere existence, as a proof for riches that the threat of socialism is real; nothing else, although it would be impossible to believe for people who grew in that hysteric environment of fear of “communism”. P. C. Roberts remarks in this regard in [10]: “In the 1960s and 1970s when the US actually had an enemy, *though possibly one of our own making ...*” (italics is mine). Indeed it was.) There was also interplay of several other factors of lesser importance.

When many ordinary people in the West were celebrating the demise of the USSR (not all, some understood what was happening), in fact they were celebrating the destruction of one of the main pillars their relative prosperity was supported by, and the decisive victory of the wealthiest class over the middle and low income classes. Their loyalty and support were not needed anymore to a ruling class, and from that time on those classes were doomed to plummeting living standards, with the middle class marked for extinction and disappearance. As it happens.

The inference from the said is clear. The wealthiest, because of their high *economic* position, present just a *socially* different class, which values only its class’ specific goals, which they satisfy mostly by means of depriving others of wealth, income, dignity, rights, all sorts of freedom, and so on. The richest may play benefactors, but they are not. In the present situation when riches do not see any real danger

for them, while they do not see a need for support from the lower socioeconomic classes, all other people will never ever find common ground with them; this class is too different, its goals will be antagonistic in principle. It's like lions do not negotiate with impalas a quota for slaughtering. All impalas are subjected to violent death, they have no choice. The rich will never backup, they could only move forward, towards the next Big Chaos they always inevitably create by pushing the rest of population to a greater and greater miseration, as the author of book [8] acknowledged by data analysis.

Stability is created for a cause by *reason*, by *measure*, but the wealthiest are driven by *instincts*, while the *reason* - the real reason, in its ancient philosophical meaning - is not the virtue they possess. Maybe few, sometimes, but that makes no difference; and if such exceptions are too different from the rest, they will be swallowed by the pack. Look at the world they are creating now (if you need a proof of that thesis), mindlessly dismantling those few foundational supporting blocks left from the previous better order, which were installed for a *cause*, a *very* sound cause, because of the necessity of stability, the necessity of the mere *survival* of the riches, not because of somebody's arbitrary good will.

Well, some people may accept subservience. Some not. But both will get pretty much nothing more in the present socioeconomic system. The only solution is substantially restricting the maximum amount of accumulated wealth and income to check the power of riches, say through reforms, legislative measures, as it was realized in 30-s, until it's too late, and to increase the wealth and income of the bottom ninety or so percent, moving the lower parts of the distribution curves on Figs. 2-5 towards the regression lines. It is not that the graphs in the lower range should coincide with regression lines. Absolutely not. This is a complicated issue, to be carefully studied and cautiously tried. It's a matter of psychology and of the life style people are trained (or tamed) for by the environment, understand they this or not. Except for the people incapable to work at all and earn income for living, everybody else should do useful work and to stress enough their abilities to earn means for living (as there is a measure in every thing, there is a measure for exertion when it gives the best results). People should work for the sake of their development, and for the development of society too, for *personal* development is impossible without moving forward, without work. But the personal development is very much impeded if the society as a whole does not move forward, does not progresses and develops. Otherwise, people *degrade*.

There will always be people inclined to stop working once they earn a bare minimum, for different reasons. But they cannot parasite on society anyway. Let them live ascetic live, if it's their choice, but not parasiting. Availability of resources across wider strata of population could stimulate peoples' development, widen their worldview; new desires, goals could appear, people could begin communicate and unite more, they could also learn more, and learn *true* things, *true* values. People and society as a whole could *grow*, could develop in a constructive, *progressive* way. However, all these "could" won't realize if some conditions are not fulfilled. The released this way human potential has to be channeled in the right ideological direction valuing both *societal* and *individual* good. If the present capitalist ideology "homo hominis lupus", and the wealth as the only worthy virtue prevail, then that will just create more ruthless competition, faster degradation, and eventually even more inequality and more miseration of the low income strata. The arrangement should be such that prosperity and progress of *society* guarantees *individual* prosperity and development, and vice versa, so that people would understand that without the one there will be no the other, and so necessarily contributed to both spheres of human life. And it's a very important principle of organization of humankind life; in fact, it is its foundation. People are inherently social creatures. This is the only reason why humans survived at all and developed. It is the strength of human society that made people strong enough to survive. Destroy the human society, and humans as such will disappear. Proof? Human children raised by animals become animals. That's why in a normal society caring about it also means caring about

yourself and your offspring and close people, and also why it is so important to have a socially healthy society.

As for the present, probably the only realistic strategy towards the riches, is to follow three prisoner's commandments: don't believe, don't be afraid, and don't ask. Actually, to not a small degree we are prisoners, slaves of socioeconomic, political and financial systems, our minds including. We must pay all sorts of taxes but have no control where and how this "public" spending goes. If we don't pay property tax, the house will be taken away. These are all attributes of the classical *slave - master* relation. Elections? Place a bet on red or on black, but zero will always win in a world governed by the money. And one more consideration - we should not feel inferior, as the wealthiest so much want us to think of ourselves. No. There is nothing special about riches as human beings to think this way. In fact, from the view of some ideologies and religions these are the richest who are the most inferior creatures. But that's another extreme. It's all a matter of reference point. The riches just try to convince us that the Golden Calf is the only true deity. Seriously?

As humans, we should all have rights, we should have opportunity for self-realization. Constitution can grant equal human rights, but for different reasons people will not be able to *exercise* these rights equally, in principle. There also should be optimal distribution of abilities exercising these rights, and maybe straight regression line in logarithmic coordinates is applicable in this case too, who knows. The same with self-realization and other rights, like housing, freedom of speech. People objectively will always have different opportunities for self-realization, but they should *have* such opportunities and means to realize them *for the good of society and themselves*, as it was said already. And, by the way, the distribution of opportunities *can* be optimal as well. How everybody will use such opportunities, is another issue.

Scientific studies confirm that children born in low, middle and high income families do not differ much in level of development at birth compared to the average, both physically and intellectually (although children of parents with low income are at the bottom of this rating, while children of the wealthiest parents are at the top). However, this difference increases many fold towards age twenty. Children of wealthy parents greatly improve their level compared to average. Middle income also secures some small improvement. However, children of low income parents noticeably degrade in all measures of development compared to their level at birth, when they were much closer to the average mark. This is what deprivation in income does, by cutting off numerous possibilities for development in low income families, which today comprise a large share of population. And when this selection goes on for generations, not only new social class originates in human "wealth and income distribution chain", in which high income class takes away resources from the low income class (as the graphs and tables presented in this study show), but physiological changes also occur in people of this class. Then such changes from epigenetic manifestations move to DNA, and here we are - indifferent senseless brutes. But brutality has a property of striking back. Brutally and destructively.

Instead of having such opportunities, what we have now is that the bottom segments of population comprising fifty or more percent are deprived of them, which otherwise would be considered as normal and natural to have in more balanced human societies. However, in most countries present socioeconomic systems are either ruled by global oligarchy, or it has strong influence on governance, mirroring in this the same Marxists' extremism of one ruling socioeconomic class. Even though riches hate Marx's ideology, de facto they adhere it no less than Bolsheviks did, usurping not only economic and political power, but also suppressing any other opinions and freedoms, and monopolizing ideological and political sphere. Through economical and political coercion they obtained the dictatorial power, which is just a substitution of dictatorship of proletariat by the dictate of the global riches, far more superseding in this Bolsheviks, whose power was nor even close to a global one. So,

what's the *principal* difference for the overwhelming majority of population residing in the low 90% stratum? I see none, other than that life *socially* and *morally* was much better in the former socialistic countries, and the social security, in all its aspects, was incomparably higher.

In the present socioeconomic systems *nobody, never ever* will give people these opportunities, nor will try to direct people's aspirations in a beneficial both for society and themselves way. Rather, the remaining things people have will be taken away. If people want these opportunities, they can be *only taken*. Very much preferable - peacefully, evolutionarily, it's still possible, and there are historical examples. The alternative is clear. The writing is indeed on the wall. Unfortunately, given the human nature, it is this alternative that will almost surely eventually prevail in most countries.

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